

Accounting Diversity and Firms' Value: A Comparative Study of Ind AS & IGAAP

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ABSTRACT

Diverse accounting practices for business reporting across the globe results in non-comparability, lack of transparency, lack of understandability, lack of relevance and lack of reliability of accounting information. Due to increasing cross border business, and the global capital market, it has become imperative to have a single understandable accounting reporting language. In view of the above fact, more than 120 countries have already adopted IFRS. India, though, has not adopted IFRS, but have converged Indian standards with IFRS in the form of Ind AS. Our research aims to study the impact of the adoption of Ind AS over the Net Worth and Total Assets of Indian manufacturing companies from 3 perspectives, i.e., Depreciation (Ind AS 16), Revenue (Ind AS 115) and Profitability as a whole. We have taken the top 37 manufacturing companies as per market capitalization and used a Regression model to measure the impact. It is inferred from the test result that adoption of Ind AS significantly influences the Net Worth & Total Assets of companies from Depreciation, Revenue and Profitability perspective. However, the adoption of Ind AS doesn't have an impact on the Total Assets of the companies from the Revenue perspective.

KEYWORDS: Ind AS, Depreciation, Revenue, Profitability, Net Worth, Total Assets.

1. INTRODUCTION

The financial reporting system is a key to economic development which consists of good governance, quality standards and established regulatory framework. It involves the disclosure of financial information to the various stakeholders about the performance and financial position of the organization over a specified period. Usually, the end product of accounting in general terms is the financial reporting practices.

With the world becoming a global village and with the liberalisation and globalisation of the economy, it becomes imperative that the disclosures and reporting of companies are made in line with that of the International regulations. India has also opened a new chapter in its accounting reform initiative with formal notification of Indian Accounting Standards (Ind AS) (Converged IFRS) issued by the Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA) on 20th February 2015. Convergence means to achieve harmony with IFRSs. In precise terms, convergence can be considered "to design and maintain national accounting standards in a way that financial statements prepared in accordance with national accounting standards comply all the requirements of IFRS and draw an unreserved statement of compliance with IFRS's. The transition from Indian GAAP to Ind AS is a historic and landmark change.

Apart from better disclosures, revised accounting standards will bring financial statements closer to economic reality. It will also ensure comparability between financial statements in line with

global standards and improve the ability of Indian companies to access funds abroad. In a notification dated 6th of April, 2016, the Ministry of Corporate Affairs through notification amended Schedule III of the Companies Act, 2013 and inserted a Division II to Schedule III w.r.t preparation of Financial Statements in compliance with Ind AS reporting practices. The major benefits of IND AS are-

- Standardised / Global training and transfer/recruitment of staff
- Comparability of entry level staff across the globe
- Comparability of financial statements enhancing investor spectrum
- Accounting work can be done offshore to avail the best quality work at the best prices.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

David *et al.* (2017) conducted a study on fair value measurement, depreciation and profitability of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. They have used a set of panel data collected from the financial reports of manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian stock exchange. For the analysis of the objectives of the paper, the statistical tool used is Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression and t-statistic. They found IFRS has a positive, but insignificant effect on depreciation and there is no significant difference in reported profit using fair value and historical cost.

Bessong and Charles (2012) made a study on IFRS adoption of the financial statements. This study adopts cross sectional analysis of the profit of manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian stock exchange by using transitory converted data of pre-IFRS of 2011 and post IFRS 2012. Simple linear regression technique and t-statistics are used for the analysis. In the study of Rodriguez-Perez *et al.* (2011) on assessing the impact of fair value effects on financial statement analysis, they applied the fair value valuation model instead of historic cost methods. They found that changing from historical cost to fair value accounting have a significant on the financial statement.

Elena *et al.* (2009) in an article on issues of convergence of US GAAPs and IFRS opined on the adoption of IFRS in the USA creating a significant change for many US companies. Adoption of IFRS would result in a more principle-based approach, greater reliance on managerial judgments and major changes in processes and systems. Callao *et al.*, 2007; Lantto and Sahlstrom, 2009; Beke, 2011; Sovbetov, 2013 and Terzil *et al.*, 2013 shows that IFRS adoption changed the financial indicators like equity position, solvency position, profitability position, total assets valuation and liquidity position on the other hand, Ağca and Aktaş, 2007; Dimitrios *et al.*, 2013; Ibiameke and Ateboh-Briggs, 2014 and Jindřichovská and Kubíčková, 2014 reveals that adoption of IFRS does not affect Financial Indicators.

3. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The Ind AS mandated to be complied with w.e.f. April-2016 was expected to impact a wide array of sectors including pharma, IT, Infra, and other manufacturing companies, for IND AS is more prescriptive than current standards and also more Elaborative, more importantly, due to the principle of fair valuation. Also, with the introduction of Ind AS, many sweeping changes have been brought into Schedule III, which was expected to ease the preparation of financial statements and thwart the fraudulent web of reporting hitherto.

As per our literature review, not much research work has been found in this context within the Indian perspective. So, our study is an attempt to find out whether the adoption of Ind AS by the companies affects the valuation and financial position of the manufacturing companies.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of this study are:

- To measure the impact of Ind AS on Net Worth of the sample manufacturing companies.
- To examine the influence of Ind AS on Total Assets of sample manufacturing companies.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

5.1 Scope of the study

The study will be focused on the analysis of the impact of Ind AS adoption on Net worth and Total Assets of top 37 manufacturing companies in India based on market capitalisation.

5.2 Sources of data

In this research work, the data are collected from secondary sources. The required data are collected from the sample companies' annual reports and other secondary sources.

5.3 Sample design

For our study, we have taken top 37 manufacturing companies in India from among the top 50 companies based on their market capitalisation, to analyse the impact of Ind AS adoption of the financial position and the value of the companies.

5.4 Sample period

We have taken Pre-Ind AS and Post-Ind AS (2015-16) study period of the sample manufacturing companies in the analysis of the objective of our study.

5.5 Variables

- Independent Variable
 - Δ DEP
 - Δ REVENUE
 - Δ PROFIT
- Dependent Variables
 - Net Worth (NW)
 - Total assets (TA)

* Δ refers to the difference of variables under Ind AS and IGAAP.

5.6 Measurement of variables

The dependent variable in this study is Net worth (NW) and Total Assets (TA). Net worth is collected from each company's financial report prepared pre-Ind AS and post-Ind AS. The NW and TA have been taken to be the difference between their values collected from the balance sheet of each company's pre and post-Ind AS annual report.

Δ DEP, Δ REVENUE and Δ PROFIT are independent variables for the study. Δ DEP is measured by taking the difference between the value of depreciation in pre-Ind AS and post-Ind AS. Similarly, Δ REVENUE and Δ PROFIT is calculated by taking the difference between their values in pre-Ind AS and in post-Ind AS.

5.7 Statistical tools & techniques

- Multicollinearity Test
- Correlation
- Multiple Regression model

5.8 Regression models

$$Y_e = \beta_0 + \beta_1\Delta\text{DEP} + \beta_2\Delta\text{REVENUE} + \beta_3\Delta\text{PROFIT}$$

Where, Y_e = Net Worth (NW)

β_0 = constant or intercept

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = slopes of independent variables

Δ DEP = Change in Depreciation;

Δ REVENUE = Change in Revenue;

Δ PROFIT = Change in Profit

Where, Y_e = Total Assets (TA)

$$Y_e = \beta_0 + \beta_1\Delta\text{DEP} + \beta_2\Delta\text{REVENUE} + \beta_3\Delta\text{PROFIT}$$

β_0 = constant or intercept

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = slopes of independent variables

Δ DEP = Change in Depreciation;

Δ REVENUE = Change in Revenue;

Δ PROFIT = Change in Profit

5.9 Hypothesis

H_{01} : Difference in values of Depreciation, Revenue and Profit of sample companies does not influence the difference in values of Net Worth, under AS and IND AS.

H_{02} : Difference in values of Depreciation, Revenue, and Profit of sample companies does not influence the difference in values of Total Assets, under AS and IND AS.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 Objective 1

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of Estimate	Change Statistics					DW
					R ² Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F	
1	0.970 ^a	0.940	0.935	1193.3903	0.940	173.687	3	33	0.000	2.150
a. Predictors: (Constant), ΔPROFIT, ΔREVENUE, ΔDEP										
b. Dependent Variable: NW										
Source: Self compiled										

The r^2 measures the percentage change independent variable due to a percentage change in the independent variable. Here the dependent variable, i.e., Net Worth is determined by the extent of 94% by the independent variables, i.e., ΔPROFIT, ΔSALES and ΔDEP combinedly. The D.W. test satisfies the rule of thumb which means there is no autocorrelation among variables. The value of D.W. test should lie between 1.5 to 2.5. The value of D.W. test as per our model is 2.15 which satisfies the rule of thumb.

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	742085556.043	3	247361852.014	173.687	0.000 ^b
Residual	46997952.169	33	1424180.369		
Total	789083508.212	36			
a. Dependent Variable: NW					
b. Predictors: (Constant), ΔPROFIT, ΔREVENUE, IndASdep					
Source: Self compiled					

Also, as per the ANOVA statistical tool, the P value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 at the 5% level of significance. So, our null hypothesis, i.e., the independent variables don't have any impact on the Net Worth of companies, is rejected. Hence, it shows that there is a significant impact of the independent variables on the Net Worth of the sample companies. The impact on the Net Worth of adoption of Ind AS may be due to the prescriptive nature of Ind AS which are more elaborative and principle based as against IGAAP which is rule based.

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	-205.179	228.649		-0.897	0.376		
ΔDEP	-27.674	1.978	-1.174	-13.991	0.000	0.256	3.903
ΔREVENUE	0.452	0.069	0.278	6.532	0.000	0.999	1.001
ΔPROFIT	-1.051	0.303	-0.291	-3.469	0.001	0.256	3.902
Source: Self compiled							
$Y_e = \beta_0 + \beta_1\Delta DEP + \beta_2\Delta REVENUE + \beta_3\Delta PROFIT$							
Where, Y_e = Net Worth (NW)							

In other words, $NW = -205.179 - 27.674\Delta DEP + 0.452\Delta REVENUE - 1.051\Delta PROFIT$

Here β_0 is the value of Net Worth, independent of all other factors or determinants. The value of β_0 is -205.179 w.r.t NW i.e., irrespective of other factors, the company would have a negative Net Worth of 205.18. The slope measures the impact of Independent variables in the respective dependent variable. Here, ΔDEP shows a negative impact of 27.674% on the NW, which means 1 unit change in ΔDEP leads to 27.674 unit change in NW in the opposite direction. ΔSALES shows a positive impact of 0.452% on NW i.e., a unit change in ΔREVENUE gives rise to 0.452 changes in NW. Also, ΔPROFIT inversely affects the NW of companies by 1.051%.

Also, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) was that "The Independent variables don't impact the Net Worth of the companies." As per coefficient result table, the P value is 0.000, 0.000, and 0.001 w.r.t ΔDEP, ΔREVENUE and ΔPROFIT, respectively, which is less than 0.05 at the 5% level of significance. So, there is no evidence to accept the null hypothesis and thus, ΔDEP, ΔREVENUE, ΔPROFIT have a significant impact on the Net Worth of the companies.

This rejection of the null hypothesis is also substantiated by the t statistics test, according to which, the t value is 13.991, 6.532, and 3.469 which is more than the 2.204, the critical value norm for 5% level of significance. Therefore, in both the tests, our alternative hypothesis H_{A1} is accepted, showing a significant impact of Δ DEP, Δ REVENUE, Δ PROFIT on the NW of the companies.

The depreciation is calculated on the fair value of assets under Ind AS. Earlier it was done at historical costs. So, this results in the change in the value of depreciation which further impacts the net worth of the company. Under Ind As Revenue recognition is principle based which changes the valuation of revenue and hence it affects the net worth of the company. The change in the value of profit under Ind AS shows the overall impact of all the various Ind ASs on the business performance which in turn influences the net worth of the company.

6.2 Objective 2

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R ² Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F	
1	0.853 ^a	0.728	0.703	1778.5309	0.728	29.444	3	33	0.000	2.049
a. Predictors: (Constant), Δ PROFIT, Δ REVENUE, IndASdep										
b. Dependent Variable: TA										
Source: Self compiled										

The r square measures the success of the regression in predicting the values of the dependent variable. Here the dependent variable, i.e., Total Assets are determined by the extent of 72.8% by the independent variables, i.e., Δ PROFIT, Δ SALES, & Δ DEP combinedly. Here, the D.W. test is 2,049 which satisfy the rule of thumb i.e. 1.5 to 2.5. It means there is no autocorrelation among variables.

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	279409369.745	3	93136456.582	29.444	0.000 ^b
Residual	104384676.744	33	3163172.023		
Total	383794046.489	36			
a. Dependent Variable: TA					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Δ PROFIT, Δ REVENUE, IndASdep					
Source: Self compiled					

Also, as per the ANOVA statistical tool, the P value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 at the 5% level of significance. So, our null hypothesis, i.e., the independent variables don't have any impact on the Total Assets of the sample companies, is rejected. In other words, it shows that the Total Assets of sample companies are being influenced significantly by the independent variables. The impact on the Net Worth of adoption of Ind AS may be due to the prescriptive nature of Ind AS which are more elaborative, and principle based as against IGAAP which is rule based.

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	-222.626	340.760	Beta	-0.653	0.518		
Δ DEP	-7.450	2.948	-0.453	-2.527	0.016	0.256	3.903
Δ REVENUE	0.124	0.103	0.110	1.206	0.236	0.999	1.001
Δ PROFIT	1.069	0.451	0.425	2.369	0.024	0.256	3.902
a. Dependent Variable: TA							
Source: Self compiled							
$Y_e = \beta_0 + \beta_1\Delta$ DEP + $\beta_2\Delta$ REVENUE + $\beta_3\Delta$ PROFIT				Where, Y_e = Total Assets (TA) β_0 = constant or intercept i.e., -222.626 β_1 = slope, i.e., -7.450 β_2 = slope, i.e., 0.124 β_3 = slope, i.e., 1.069			

In other words, $TA = -222.626 - 7.450\Delta$ DEP + 0.124Δ REVENUE + 1.069Δ PROFIT

Here β_0 is the value of Net Worth, independent of all other factors or determinants. The value of β_0 is -222.626 w.r.t TA i.e., irrespective of other factors, the company would have a negative Total Assets of 222.626. The slope here measures the impact of Independent variables in the respective dependent variable. Here, Δ DEP shows an inverse impact of 7.450% on TA, which means 1 unit change in Δ DEP leads to 7.450 unit change in TA in the reverse direction. Δ SALES (Δ REVENUE) shows a positive impact of 0.124% on TA i.e., a unit change in Δ REVENUE gives rise to 0.124 changes in TA. Also, Δ PROFIT influences the TA of sample companies by 1.069% in the same direction.

Also, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) was that "The Independent variables don't influence the Total Assets of the companies." As per coefficient result table, the P value is 0.016, and 0.024 w.r.t Δ DEP, and Δ PROFIT, respectively, which is less than 0.05 at the 5% level of significance. So, there is no evidence to accept the null hypothesis and thus, Δ DEP, and Δ PROFIT has a significant influence on the Total Assets of the sample companies. However, the P value, as per the coefficient table, is 0.236 (i.e., >0.05) w.r.t to Δ REVENUE, which means the acceptance of the null hypothesis that Δ SALES (Δ REVENUE) doesn't influence the Total Assets of the sample companies.

This rejection of the null hypothesis is also substantiated by the t statistics test, according to which, the t value is 2.527, and 2.369 which is more than the 2.204 the critical value norm for 5% level of significance. Therefore, in both the tests, our alternative hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted, showing a significant influence of Δ DEP, and Δ PROFIT on TA of the sample companies. However, it is not so in the case of Δ SALES (Δ REVENUE) influence on Total Assets, as the t value of 1.206 as against Δ REVENUE is within the critical value limit of 2.204.

The depreciation is calculated on the fair value of assets under Ind AS. Earlier it was done at historical costs. So, this results in the change in the value of depreciation which further impacts the net worth of the company. Under Ind As Revenue recognition is principle based which changes the valuation of revenue and hence it affects the net worth of the company. The change in the value of profit under Ind AS shows the overall impact of all the various Ind ASs on the business performance which in turn influences the net worth of the company.

7. FINDINGS

- There is a significant influence of differences in values of Depreciation on the differences in values of Net Worth and Total Assets of the sample companies, under AS and Ind AS.
- There is an impact of differences in values of Profitability on the differences in values of Net Worth and Total Assets of the sample companies, under AS and Ind AS.
- The differences in values of Revenue have a significant effect on the differences in values of Net Worth of the sample companies, under AS and Ind AS.
- There is no significant influence of differences in values of Revenue on the differences in values of Total Assets of the sample companies, under AS and Ind AS.

8. CONCLUSION

Indian Accounting Standards (IND AS) represents fair value measurement, composite depreciation, reclassification of some assets, etc. Previous studies have shown that adoption of IFRS and its impact on financial performance in International context; so, the researchers intended to find out the significant difference between the valuation of accounting practices under AS and Ind AS. The aim of this paper was to measure the impact of Ind As on Net Worth and Total Assets of sample manufacturing companies in India. For the study, 37 manufacturing companies selected out of the top 100 listed companies in India on the basis of market capitalisation. The data has been collected from financial reports of individual companies. Ind AS is measured by calculating the difference between Ind AS value and IGAAP value. In this study, researchers have selected Net Worth and Total Assets as the dependent variable and Depreciation, Revenue and profit as independent variables. The Regression model has been used for data analysis. The results show that there is a significant difference in the valuation of accounting practices for depreciation, revenue and profit between AS and Ind AS.

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